

CRUCIFORM SPECIMEN DESIGNS FOR PLANAR BIAXIAL FATIGUE TESTING IN COMPOSITES

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INTRODUCTION

The usage of cruciform specimen for planar biaxial coupon testing in a multi-scale multi-axial fatigue testing and modelling scheme is evaluated using finite element analysis. Nine cruciform designs made up of a multidirectional $[0/\theta/0/-\theta]_s$ laminate, where $\theta = 60^\circ$, are simulated under a biaxial loading state to test the uniformity of the local stress state and the global strain state in the off-axis layer and on the surface of the biaxial zone respectively. The biaxial zone of all the cruciform designs had the same strain state of $\epsilon_{XX} = 5000\mu\text{strain}$ and $\epsilon_{YY} = 2500\mu\text{strain}$. The learnings from this analysis though valid for the current loading condition, is a step towards finding a possible 'one for all material configuration' cruciform specimen design in the future.

CRUCIFORM GEOMETRIES

STRESS/STRAIN STATE UNIFORMITY

Fig 1. Nine cruciform specimens considered in this study. Dimensions in mm.

Fig 2. ϵ_{XX}^* and ϵ_{YY}^* distribution on the surface. Here, $\epsilon_{nn}^* = \epsilon_{nn|FE} / \epsilon_{nn|REQ}$, where $nn = XX$ or YY represents the global directions and $\epsilon_{nn|REQ}$ are the required strains.
Fig 3. σ_{11}^* and σ_{22}^* distribution in the $\theta = 60^\circ$ ply. Here, $\sigma_{nn}^* = \sigma_{nn|FE} / \sigma_{nn|CLT}$, where $nn = 11$ or 22 represents the local coordinate system directions.

LOAD SHARING

Fig 4. Forces required to recreate the global strain state of $\epsilon_{XX} = 5000\mu\text{ strain}$ and $\epsilon_{YY} = 2500\mu\text{strain}$ in the biaxial zone. The specimens with the least pair of forces has a better reduction in the load sharing capability between the adjacent arms and the biaxial zone.

CONCLUSIONS

The circular and the rhombus-shaped biaxial zones had better uniformity in both the global strain state and the local stress state than the square-shaped biaxial zone. However, the rhombus-shaped biaxial zone required higher forces than the circular and the square-shaped biaxial zone to recreate the same strain state within the same type with the latter requiring the least forces. In general, the reduction in load sharing was better in Type 2 and Type 3 specimens than in Type 1 specimens. The highest stress concentration for Type 2 and Type 3 specimens was at the slot tips whereas for Type 1 specimens was at the inner corner radius fillet.

A MULTI-SCALE MULTI-AXIAL FATIGUE TESTING AND MODELING SCHEME

